

Observations on the trapdoor spider *Ancylotrypa nigriceps* (Purcell, 1902) (Araneae: Cyrtaucheniidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Ancylotrypa* Simon, 1889 is a genus known from 43 species endemic to Africa, with 29 species known from South Africa. They are large ground-dwelling trapdoor spiders that live in burrows that are closed with a wafer lid. Although it is a large genus, little is still known about their general behaviour. The general morphology, behaviour and distribution, along with images of live specimens of the species *Ancylotrypa nigriceps* (Purcell, 1902) that is known from Gauteng and the Free State in South Africa are discussed.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Ancylotrypa*, described by Simon (1889), is known as the African wafer-lid trapdoor spiders. This African endemic genus is represented by 43 species, of which 29 are known from South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020; World Spider Catalog, 2022).

Species of *Ancylotrypa* live in silk-lined burrows of which the depth varies between species, with the main portion being as deep as 32 cm. The shape of the burrows varies from single burrows, to Y-shaped to the shape of a curved pipe. In some species, side chambers are made with or without lids (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), spiders were sampled throughout the country (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). During SANSA surveys in the Gauteng and Free State provinces, the species *Ancylotrypa nigriceps* (Purcell, 1902) were frequently sampled. We provide more information on its general morphology, behaviour, and distribution, along with images of live specimens.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled during SANSA surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria. Series of photographs were taken by the second author (JVZ) in Gauteng.

TAXONOMIC NOTES

A South African endemic, described by Purcell (1902) as *Cyrtauchenius nigriceps* from Johannesburg. Although the species is presently known from only one sex, it has a wide geographical range and can be listed as being of Least Concern.

Ancylotrypa nigriceps (Purcell, 1902)

Cyrtauchenius nigriceps Purcell, 1902: 358.

Pelmatorycter nigriceps: Simon, 1903: 899.

Ancylotrypa nigriceps: Roewer, 1942: 169; Raven, 1985: 157;

Dippenaar-Schoeman 2002: 47; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020: 21.

Diagnostic characteristics: Male. Carapace reddish brown, the cephalic portion blackish brown; chelicerae dark; legs and pedipalps, including the coxae, and the sternum pale ochraceous; abdomen pale yellowish below and at the sides, blackish brown above (Figs 1 & 2). Carapace longer than wide, with a row of stout, curved, marginal spines on each side above the bases of the posterior pairs of legs (Fig. 3); cephalic region strongly arched,

Figures 1–2: *Ancylotrypa nigriceps*: 1–2. Male from Heidelberg, Gauteng, found in grassland. Photo credits: Johan van Zyl.

posteriorly narrowed; fovea broad, procurved; clypeus narrow; chelicerae broad, rastellum with several short, blunt spines on low mound. Sternum posteriorly broad; posterior sigilla large, oval abdomen sometimes without bands or spots (Fig. 4); tarsus II with four small spines; tarsus IV with a distal group of small spines internally and double series of longer spines externally. Female unknown.

Figures 3–7: *Ancylotrypa nigriceps* male from Erfenisdam Nature Reserve (alcohol material): 3. Dorsal view. 4. Ventral view. 5. Eye pattern. 6. Male palp. Photo credits: Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Free State: Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.5, 26.8); Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68). **Gauteng:** Roodepoort (Honingklip) (-26.14, 27.86); Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53); Heidelberg, Van Riebeeck Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16); Irene Holgatfontein (-26.27, 28.49)*; Luipaardsvlei (-26.14, 27.79)*; Zwartkoppies (-25.75, 28.37)*.

KwaZulu-Natal: Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.54, 32.17)

* Sampled by Engelbrecht (2013).

LIFESTYLE

Of the 29 species of *Ancylotrypa* known from South Africa, little is known about their behaviour. In Dippenaar-Schoeman (2002), burrows of seven species are discussed as observed by Hewitt (1915; 1919); Purcell (1903), and Van Dam & Roberts (1917). The vertical, silk-lined burrows are made in habitats ranging from grassy areas to open, barren ground and are frequently found under logs, stones, or rock overhangs, which afford shelter. The depth of the burrow varies between species with the main portion being as deep as 32 cm. Burrow shapes vary from simple to Y- or U-shaped. In some species side chambers are made with or without lids.

A male *A. nigriceps* was observed and photographed in a silk-lined burrow in Heidelberg, Gauteng. It was in a vertical, silk-lined burrow. The burrow was found in a grassy area in open, barren ground. The entrance is very well camouflaged (Fig. 12) and is closed over with a soft silk flap, and well camouflaged with sand particles (Fig. 7). The flap was a floppy extension of the burrow itself and, when open, it forms a rim around the burrow entrance on the ground (Fig. 8). To close it, the spider lifts the flap and pulls it towards the centre, forming a sand-covered trapdoor (Fig. 12). During the day, most of the spiders retire to the lower portion of the burrow. Here the male takes up position in the burrow entrance, waiting for prey that is grabbed and immediately pulled into the burrow (Figs 9–12). During surveys in the grassland at Irene, an immature female was sampled and photographed that might be the undescribed female of *A. nigriceps* (Fig. 13).

Figures 7–12. *Ancylotrypa nigriceps* male catching a beetle, pulling it into its burrow. Photo credits: Johan van Zyl.

Figure 13. Possibly the female of *Ancylotrypa nigriceps* photographed from Irene (undescribed). Photo credit: Peter Webb.

The males are more active and are more easily collected in pitfall traps (Engelbrecht, 2013). In built-up areas they frequently drown in swimming pools. In South Africa they have been mainly sampled from the Grassland Biome (Haddad *et al.*, 2013) and Savanna Biome (Foord *et al.*, 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES

Although the species is presently known from only one sex, it has a fairly wide geographical range and it is protected in the Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (Haddad *et al.*, 2015), Amanzi Private Game Reserve (Haddad & Butler, 2018), Ndumo Game Reserve, and Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve. It is possibly under-sampled and is listed as Least Concern.

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